

Research methodology

A simple and rapid method for isolation of bacterial genomic DNA

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The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is now an important tool for ecological studies because of its simplicity and capacity to rapidly screen a large number of samples with a minimal amount of DNA. It is especially useful for studying the population biology of plant pathogens, such as *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) (which causes bacterial blight of rice), where massive sampling is required for analysis. While it is possible to obtain PCR fingerprints directly using whole bacterial cells, more consistent results are obtained using good-quality DNA as a template. Genomic DNA is isolated in a multistep process, typically involving sodium dodecyl sulfate-mediated cell lysis. DNA extraction, alcohol precipitation, and ethanol wash. Because it is a lengthy process, the isolation of genomic DNA is a bottleneck in large-scale application of PCR as a fingerprinting tool.

Here we report a simple alcohol lysis procedure to isolate PCR-quality genomic DNA of bacterial cells. In this method, ethanol functions both to lyse the cells and to precipitate the DNA. Cells from *Xoo*, *X. o. pv. oryzicola*, *Pseudomonas blumei*, *Burkholderia glumae*, *Asorhizobium* sp., and *Escherichia coli* plate cultures were collected using the wide end of a sterile toothpick (Fig. 1) and washed in 400 μ l of water to remove the extracellular polysaccharides. Cells were pelleted in a microcentrifuge by spinning for 2 min (12,400 rpm) and the still turbid supernatant was discarded. The cells were resuspended in the residual liquid, and 200 μ l of 95% ethanol was added to a final concentration of approximately 70% alcohol. After 10-30 min, the suspension was spun for 30 s to pellet the cell debris, and the supernatant was transferred to a new tube. DNA was pelleted by spinning for 5 min, dried, and

then dissolved in 10 μ l of sterile water. To check the viability of the ethanol-treated cells, the pelleted cells were resuspended in the residual alcohol, and the whole suspension was plated.

One μ l of the DNA preparation was used as template in a 25- μ l reaction volume. Primers corresponding to conserved sequences in bacterial repetitive elements (REP1R-I, 5'IIICGICGICATCIGGC 3' and REP2-I, 5'ICGICTTATCIGGCCTAC 3') were used for all the strains under conditions prescribed for rep-PCR. Additionally for the *Xanthomonas* strains, 0.5 μ M of the primers JEL1 (5'CTCAGGTCAGGTCGCC 3') and JEL2 (5'GCTCTACAATCGTCCGC 3') were used with 185 μ M each of four dNTPs. approximately 2.5 units of Taq polymerase in an incubation buffer amended with 10% dimethylsulfoxide (v/v) and 7.5 μ l of 1 M Tris, pH 9.5. The reaction mixture was initially denatured for 1 min at 94 $^{\circ}$ C and then subjected to 30 cycles of PCR (10s denaturation at 94 $^{\circ}$ C, 1 min annealing at 62 $^{\circ}$ C, and 10 min extension at 65 $^{\circ}$ C) and a final extension for 15 min at 65 $^{\circ}$ C using a Perkin Elmer Cetus DNA thermal cycler. The PCR products were resolved in a gel containing 0.5% agarose and 0.75% SynergelTM, visualized by staining with ethidium bromide and photographed using Polaroid 667 film.

1. Cells collected using a sterile toothpick from a 3-d-old plate culture of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*. DNA isolated from the cells by the alcohol lysis method was resuspended in 10 μ l of water, and 1 μ l was used as a template for PCR amplification.

With DNA prepared by this method as template for PCR, fingerprint patterns generally comparable with those obtained using DNA prepared by conventional means were obtained from 3-d-old, 1-wk-old, and 5-wk-old plate cultures, and from 1-d-old broth culture (Fig. 2). Similar patterns were also obtained from cells stored in ethanol for 6 wk prior to DNA isolation.

The alcohol lysis method is simple and fast, requiring about 15 min, and produces enough DNA for several amplification reactions. It also renders cells nonviable and thus suitable for storage and transport and eventual PCR fingerprinting of pathogen sample ex situ. ■

2. PCR fingerprint patterns of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains PX0215 (A), PX0143 (B), PX01 (C) and PX0204 using template DNA prepared by the potassium acetate method (lanes 1, 6, 11, and 16), and by the alcohol lysis method using 3-d old (lanes 2, 7, 12, and 17), 1-wk-old (lanes 3, 8, 13, and 18), and 5-wk-old (lanes 4, 9, 14, and 19) plate cultures, and from 1-d-old broth cultures (lanes 5, 10, 15, and 19). The primers used in the PCR method were JEL1/JEL2. The DNA molecular size markers are on the lanes labeled M on the left (1-kb ladder) and right (BioMarker EXT).